

The Lens Licence of Global Patent Information for RLA

ARDC RLA PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1. PROJECT INFORMATION

PROJECT TITLE AND CODE	The Lens licence of Global Patent Information for RLA
PROJECT START AND END DATES	31 May 2024 - 30 November 2024
LEAD CONTRACTING ORGANISATION	Cambia (DBA The Lens)
SUBCONTRACTOR REPRESENTATIVE	N/A
PROJECT LEAD CONTACT PERSON	Aaron Ballagh
PROJECT MANAGER	Aaron Ballagh, Mingfang Wu
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	N/A
FOCUS AREA and ACTIVITY	Research Link Australia

1.1 Background

The Lens currently supports users around the world with global patent metadata. The data not only includes the vast majority of patents from Australia, but also the majority of patents globally and is enriched with supplementary data and linked through a multi-silo citation graph.

Through this project, The Lens provided access to regularly updated metadata for global patent information for integration into ARDC's Research Link Australia (RLA) platform, supporting the development of the platform and goals of the RLA project. This project has delivered collections of patents for Australian universities and research institutions as well as individual Australia researchers who have linked their patents to their ORCID record, integrated into the RLA platform providing relevant and valuable information for stakeholders.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

The project aimed to enable seamless integration of enriched patent metadata from The Lens into ARDC's Research Link Australia (RLA) platform to enhance its functionality and value for stakeholders. The project focused on three key objectives: establishing access to The Lens API and training ARDC on

its use; integrating and testing the metadata within the RLA platform to support capabilities and stakeholder use cases; and gathering stakeholder feedback to evaluate the integration’s impact and inform future recommendations. The project also explored the potential for transitioning the trial into a production environment and business as usual (BAU) to ensure long-term sustainability. The project successfully integrated global patent metadata from The Lens into the RLA platform, making the platform more relevant and valuable for stakeholders by situating Australian innovation within an international context. The Lens provided a one-year license for utilizing and updating the patent metadata via API access. Additionally, The Lens provided guidance on the integration of patent metadata, supporting its combination with other datasets for presentation on the RLA platform and further exploration by project collaborators. Feedback from RLA stakeholders was sought and received, with the majority of feedback being positive, and included suggestions for future enhancements.

1.3 Summary of value

The collaboration between ARDC and The Lens has delivered significant value by integrating mature patent information and domain expertise into the Research Link Australia (RLA) platform. This partnership aligns with ARDC’s strategy to engage with platforms that enhance access to information and innovation, enriching the understanding of relationships within the broader research and innovation ecosystem. The addition of global patent data for Australian institutions and researchers has already provided valuable insights for stakeholders, helping to identify and showcase research and innovation capabilities within Australia. Looking ahead, if implemented in production, this integration will enable end users to discover relevant patent information through RLA and seamlessly explore The Lens system for deeper, more connected insights, fostering further innovation and collaboration opportunities.

2. DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1. Achievements against project work packages/deliverables:

Use the following criteria and colours to assign a status to each work package:

Status Key

Completed	Completed
Non Completion may impact on project outcomes	Not yet completed and non-completion may have some impact on the project outcomes. Delay has been accepted by the Steering Committee and responsibility for completion has been assigned.
Will not be completed and will impact on project outcomes	Will not be completed and has an impact on the project outcomes. The Steering committee has accepted the non-completion and understands the impact to the project outcomes.

DELIVERABLE / WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION (INCLUDE LINKS TO RELEVANT DOCUMENTATION)	AGREED DUE DATE	ACTUAL or EXPECTED	STATUS
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			COMPLETION DATE	
WP1 Getting Started, Enabling Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 1.1: Licence and Access provisioning - enabling API access. (confirmed by steering committee) • Deliverable 1.2: Training on Lens API and metadata (delivery confirmed) • Deliverable 1.3: ARDC RLA test queries/harvests Lens data (confirmed by steering committee) 	30/06/2024	30/06/2024	Completed
WP2 RLA platform and portal testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 2.1: ARDC RLA integrates data into RLA platform graph and updates portal (in test RLA system, not production) (delivery confirmed) • Deliverable 2.2: The Lens and RLA review changes in RLA test (confirmed by steering committee) including linking approach from RLA pages/data to the Lens Platform • Deliverable 2.3: The Lens and RLA consider limited release into production (for the trial/project period) (confirmed by steering committee) 	31/10/2024	14/11/2024	Completed
WP3 Review of next steps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 3.1: RLA stakeholder feedback and consultation on the integration and value • Deliverable 3.2: The Lens and RLA to provide final reports including: project/trial summary and recommendations, future licensing recommendations, transitioning to BAU. 	30/11/2024	30/11/2024	Completed

2.2. Project outputs and outcomes

2.2.1 Outputs

OUTPUTS	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
Recommendation for future relationship with RLA and The Lens /Cambia	Provided to ARDC as part of this final report.	Recommendations provided to ARDC.
A successful trial of Global Patent information in the RLA platform	Demo platform released: 17 Oct The required indicator was for RLA to be able to undertake stakeholder feedback on the integration and value. Stakeholder feedback was sought starting 19 Nov.	Global patents for Australia research institutions and researchers in the RLA demo platform. Feedback from RLA stakeholders.
A successful trial of integration into the RLA platform	The required indicator was RLA links to patent information and to The Lens platform. This was successfully achieved in a demonstration RLA system on 14/11/2024.	Lens patent queries were created for 52 Australian universities and research institutions for a total of 65,543 Lens patents linked in RLA. There are 387 inventors in RLA with Lens patents associated with their ORCID record for a total of 8,841 patents linked in RLA.

2.2.2 Outcomes

OUTCOME	RESULTS SUMMARY	EVIDENCE
Users accessing/discovering patent information	Indications of the need and value for this information (from user feedback and consultation)	RLA stakeholder feedback provided on the value of integrated patent information.
Identification of innovation/research/industry links	Number of links (research industry connections) identified in the RLA platform data	Increased number of links between Australian researchers/research institutions and patents in the RLA platform data.

2.3. Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
Review and feedback	Seeking feedback from stakeholders on the usefulness of the presented patent data in RLA and further enhancements	20 - RLA co-design workshop. 11 - RLA project partners and relevant stakeholders contacted directly.	19/11/2024 - 30/11/2024

3. PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment. Please complete the following sections as relevant to your program.

3.1. Impact stories

The Lens patent data was fully available in the RLA demo platform two weeks prior to the end of the project. This provided time for request feedback from stakeholders, but not enough time for the project to have a significant impact given the lifespan of typical research projects, however positive feedback from stakeholders was received and is summarised below.

Value of Patent Data:

- Patents as indicators of research impact and utility, particularly for identifying where research outputs have been referenced or applied (e.g., in industry patents).
- Patent data demonstrates research intent to translate knowledge into commercial value, appealing to industry partners.

Applications in Partnerships:

- Facilitates identifying potential funding partners and collaborators (e.g., organisations referencing similar research in patents).
- Useful for understanding ownership and rights in due diligence processes for projects or commercial arrangements.

Strategic Insights:

- Combining funding, publications, and patent data offers new analytical possibilities for identifying expertise, guiding collaborations, and driving innovation.
- Can support conversations with government and industry about funding opportunities or partnerships.

Organisational Use Cases:

- Some organisations focus less on patents due to public-good-oriented funding but acknowledge potential future applicability as funding streams evolve.
- Universities' varied approaches to patents (e.g., partnering with industry for commercialisation) reflect differing strategic priorities.

Systemic Challenges and Opportunities:

- Australia's current reliance on personal relationships for academia-industry links highlights the need for systematic tools like RLA.
- Improved integration between academia and industry is critical for future-proofing the economy and fostering innovation.
- Building confidence among stakeholders, including funding contributors, by showcasing research capability and alignment.

In addition to the positive stakeholder feedback and as a direct outcome of this project, The Lens enhanced its patent data capabilities by indexing the Inventor ORCID identifier field and exposing it for all users. This addition improves the discoverability of inventors across The Lens platform and allows for systematic linking of Australian inventors with their patent in RLA, strengthening connections between patents and individual researcher profiles.

Available since [Release 9.3](#), the Inventor ORCID field is now accessible to all users on the Lens.org platform (e.g. <https://link.lens.org/JtB35tGgNab>), in the JSON Lines export files, and in the [API response](#). [Lens Profiles](#), which are available for inventors and researchers to claim their works/patents and sync them to their ORCID record, provide a mechanism for further enhancing the coverage of inventor ORCID identifiers, which will feed back into the RLA platform.

3.2. Impact metrics

3.2.1. Use, Outreach and Communications Metrics

ARDC realises that a number of possible impact metrics are lag indicators.

IMPACT METRIC	PROJECT TOTAL TO DATE	DESCRIPTION, LINKS and DOIs
Number of datasets published (preferably with record in Research Link Australia)	N/A	Demo site only released. Future impact measures can include the number of referrals from ARDC RLA to The Lens.
Number of publications citing project or project outputs	N/A	
Number of publications that cite /reference the infrastructure or service	N/A	

Current number of users	N/A	
Number of researchers trained (online or face-to-face)	N/A	
Availability of the infrastructure (days in operation vs days offline)	101	Lens Patent information was available in the RLA demo site from 22 Aug, with data fully integrated on 14 November.
Number of outreach activities (e.g. seminars, presentations)	0	Expect to start when The Lens patent connections are in RLA production.
Social media mentions	0	
Blog posts/news articles that reference infrastructure or service	2	The Lens Newsletter (Release 9.3) https://mailchi.mp/lens/release-8-10713294 . ARDC RLA project page https://ardc.edu.au/project/the-lens-global-patent-information-for-rla/

3.2.2. Links to Publications and Other Communications

Blog posts/news articles that reference the platform/infrastructure

DATE	LINK
Sept 2024	ARDC RLA project announced in The Lens Newsletter (Release 9.3) https://mailchi.mp/lens/release-8-10713294
Sept 2024	ARDC RLA project page https://ardc.edu.au/project/the-lens-global-patent-information-for-rla/

3.2.3. Details on users of the platform

The RLA demo has only been available for a couple weeks, so the volume of users is not applicable. The demo site was shared with 11 individuals from 6 early stakeholder organisations for feedback, including universities and government research organisations.

4. LESSONS LEARNED

4.1. What Went Well?

The project was able to successfully demonstrate integrating global patent metadata from The Lens into the RLA platform, with initial feedback from stakeholders strongly indicating this will be “useful”, “valuable” and for some extremely useful. A number of stakeholders have provided specific feedback on links and features that would make this information even more useful. The collaboration between ARDC and The Lens has shown it can deliver significant value. Looking ahead to implementation, this integration is expected to enable end users with deeper and more connected insights, fostering further innovation and collaboration opportunities.

4.2. What Could be Improved?

A number of enhancements and features were suggested by RLA stakeholders after sharing the demo RLA platform for feedback, these include:

- Add patent citations and linked citing patent metadata for Australian researchers, universities and research institutions.
- Engage with commercialisation offices or patent attorney / law firms to understand broader use cases.
- Patent searches linked to related publications/projects.
- APIs to expose more data for integration and usability.
- Enable keyword searches for patents.